

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to ####)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Note

Previously authors used 'XXXX' as placeholder for the highest integer representable by four concatenated digits, thus AAAA₁₁, BBBB₁₂, CCCC₁₃, DDDD₁₄, EEEE₁₅ and FFFF₁₆ in base 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 respectively. In the context of base 11 up to 33, the 'XXXX' placeholder is unambiguous, as 'XXXX' cannot represent a valid integer.

However, in the context of base 34 and up, the 'XXXX' placeholder becomes ambiguous, as 'XXXX' can be interpreted as valid integer, for example XXXX₃₆ in case of base 36.

Within this manuscript authors used '####' as placeholder for the highest integer representable by four concatenated digits, for example ZZZZ₃₆ in case of base 36.

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 16 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	A	B	C	D	E	F	+	-	*	/	^	(	)
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Digits 1 up to F occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
-------------------------------	-----------------------------------

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45*-(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(-(1+2)+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9))*ABCDEF)$	$-(FEDCBA*(9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Definition - Base 17 up to 36 Crazy Sequential Representations

Identical to base 16 crazy sequential representations, but more digits allowed:

17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
1-G	1-H	1-I	1-J	1-K	1-L	1-M	1-N	1-O	1-P	1-Q	1-R	1-S	1-T	1-U	1-V	1-W	1-X	1-Y	1-Z

Aim

Identify genuine base 17 up to 36 crazy sequential representations for '0000 up to #####'

- Genuine base 17 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to GGGG
- Genuine base 18 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to HHHH
[...]
- Genuine base 35 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to YYYY [....] [....]
- Genuine base 36 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to ZZZZ

Generalization

Given that...

$((X+0) - ((X+1) + (X+2) - (X+3)))$	$== 0$
$((X+0) - ((X+1) + (X+2) - (X+3))) * (...)$	$== 0$
$((X+3) - ((X+2) + (X+1) - (X+0)))$	$== 0$
$(...) * ((X+3) - ((X+2) + (X+1) - (X+0)))$	$== 0$

Any base 'n' crazy sequential representation without concatenation...

248_{10}	$1/2 * 3 * 4^5 / 6 - 7 + 8 - 9$
150_{10}	$9 * 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4^3 / 2 - 1$
374_{10}	$(1 + 2 * 3)^4 - 5 * (6 + 7 * 8) + 9 - (A + B * C * D)$
343_{10}	$D + C * (B * A) / (9 * 8 - 7 - 6 * (5 + 4) - 3 * 2 - 1)$

...can be converted to a base 'n+4' crazy sequential representation...

248_{10}	$1/2 * 3 * 4^5 / 6 - 7 + 8 - 9 + (A - (B + C - D))$
150_{10}	$(D - (C + B - A)) + 9 * 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4^3 / 2 - 1$
374_{10}	$(1 + 2 * 3)^4 - 5 * (6 + 7 * 8) + 9 - (A + B * C * D) + (E - (F + G - H))$
343_{10}	$(H - (G + F - E)) + D + C * (B * A) / (9 * 8 - 7 - 6 * (5 + 4) - 3 * 2 - 1)$

...and a base '>n+4' crazy sequential representation...

248_{10}	$1/2 * 3 * 4^5 / 6 - 7 + 8 - 9 + (A - (B + C - D)) * (E ...)$
150_{10}	$(... E) * (D - (C + B - A)) + 9 * 8 + 7 * 6 + 5 + 4^3 / 2 - 1$
374_{10}	$(1 + 2 * 3)^4 - 5 * (6 + 7 * 8) + 9 - (A + B * C * D) + (E - (F + G - H)) * (I ...)$
343_{10}	$(... I) * (H - (G + F - E)) + D + C * (B * A) / (9 * 8 - 7 - 6 * (5 + 4) - 3 * 2 - 1)$

...by using the '(digit-(digit+digit-digit))' construct, which always evaluates to zero...

248_{10}	$(248_{10}) + (0)$
150_{10}	$(0) + (150_{10})$
374_{10}	$(375_{10}) + (0)$
343_{10}	$(0) + (343_{10})$

...and therefor never influences the evaluation result.

Therefor the '0000 up to ####' range can be completed for base 17 up to 36 by identifying a relatively small set of genuine crazy sequential representations without concatenation:

From	To	To	Base	Series
0000000 ₁₀	0083520 ₁₀	GGGG ₁₇	<= 13	Base 17 to 36
0083521 ₁₀	0104975 ₁₀	HHHH ₁₈	<= 14	Base 18 to 36
0104976 ₁₀	0130320 ₁₀	IIII ₁₉	<= 15	Base 19 to 36
0130321 ₁₀	0159999 ₁₀	JJJJ ₂₀	<= 16	Base 20 to 36
0160000 ₁₀	0194480 ₁₀	KKKK ₂₁	<= 17	Base 21 to 36
0194481 ₁₀	0234255 ₁₀	LLLL ₂₂	<= 18	Base 22 to 36
0234256 ₁₀	0279840 ₁₀	MMMM ₂₃	<= 19	Base 23 to 36
0279841 ₁₀	0331775 ₁₀	NNNN ₂₄	<= 20	Base 24 to 36
0331776 ₁₀	0390624 ₁₀	O000 ₂₅	<= 21	Base 25 to 36
0390625 ₁₀	0456975 ₁₀	PPPP ₂₆	<= 22	Base 26 to 36
0456976 ₁₀	0531440 ₁₀	QQQQ ₂₇	<= 23	Base 27 to 36
0531441 ₁₀	0614655 ₁₀	RRRR ₂₈	<= 24	Base 28 to 36
0614656 ₁₀	0707280 ₁₀	SSSS ₂₉	<= 25	Base 29 to 36
0707281 ₁₀	0809999 ₁₀	TTTT ₃₀	<= 26	Base 30 to 36
0810000 ₁₀	0923520 ₁₀	UUUU ₃₁	<= 27	Base 31 to 36
0923521 ₁₀	1048575 ₁₀	VVVV ₃₂	<= 28	Base 32 to 36
1048576 ₁₀	1185920 ₁₀	WWWW ₃₃	<= 29	Base 33 to 36
1185921 ₁₀	1336335 ₁₀	XXXX ₃₄	<= 30	Base 34 to 36
1336336 ₁₀	1500624 ₁₀	YYYY ₃₅	<= 31	Base 35 to 36
1500625 ₁₀	1679615 ₁₀	ZZZZ ₃₆	<= 32	Base 36 to 36

For example, genuine base 17 up to 36 crazy sequential representations for 83800₁₀ can be derived from two genuine base 11 crazy sequential representations without concatenation:

Integer	Base	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
83800 ₁₀	11	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A
	17	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-(C+D-E))*(FG)
	18	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-(C+D-E))*(FGH)
	19	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-(C+D-E))*(FGHI)
	29	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-(C+D-E))*(FGHIJ)
	21	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-(C+D-E))*(FGHIJK)
	[..]	[.....]
36	-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-(C+D-E))*(FG...Z)	
83800 ₁₀	11	A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))
	17	(GF)*(E-(D+C-B))+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))
	18	(HGF)*(E-(D+C-B))+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))
	19	(IHGF)*(E-(D+C-B))+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))
	29	(JIHGF)*(E-(D+C-B))+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))
	21	(KJIHGF)*(E-(D+C-B))+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))
	[..]	[.....]
36	(Z...GF)*(E-(D+C-B))+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^(-4+3-2)+1))	

Results

Authors completed the ‘0000 up to #####’ range for base 17 up to 36 (see supplement).

Increasing variants were tabulated as follows:

Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
11212 ₁₀	$1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-(D+E-F))*...$
13938 ₁₀	$(1+2)^(3+4)*5+6*7*8*9-A-B+(C-(D+E-F))*...$
22207 ₁₀	$(1+2^3)^4-5^6*(7-8)^9+A+B+(C-(D+E-F))*...$
68190 ₁₀	$(1*2*3*4*5^(6+7-8)+9)*A/B+(C-(D+E-F))*...$

In order to ‘increase the base’ insert ‘sufficient digits’ at the ‘...’ position:

Base	Integer	Integer	Crazy Sequential Representation
17	24D9 ₁₇	11212 ₁₀	$1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-(D+E-F))*G$
18	1GAG ₁₈	11212 ₁₀	$1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-(D+E-F))*GH$
19	1C12 ₁₉	11212 ₁₀	$1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-(D+E-F))*GHI$
20	180C ₂₀	11212 ₁₀	$1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-(D+E-F))*GHIJ$
[..]	[.....]	[.....]	[.....]
36	08NG ₃₆	11212 ₁₀	$1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-(D+E-F))*G..Z$

Decreasing variants were tabulated as follows:

Integer	Crazy Sequential Representation
13874 ₁₀	$...*(F-(E+D-C))+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
18268 ₁₀	$...*(F-(E+D-C))+B*A+9+(8+7*6^5+4+3)/(2+1)$
43402 ₁₀	$...*(F-(E+D-C))+B-A-9*(8*7-(6+5)^4/3+2)^1$
48345 ₁₀	$...*(F-(E+D-C))+B/A*(9+8+7+(6+5)^4*3+2+1)$

In order to ‘increase the base’ insert ‘sufficient digits’ at the ‘...’ position;

Base	Integer	Integer	Crazy Sequential Representation
17	2E02 ₁₇	13874 ₁₀	$...G*(F-(E+D-C))+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
18	26EE ₁₈	13874 ₁₀	$..HG*(F-(E+D-C))+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
19	2084 ₁₉	13874 ₁₀	$.IHG*(F-(E+D-C))+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
20	1EDE ₂₀	13874 ₁₀	$JIHG*(F-(E+D-C))+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$
[..]	[.....]	[.....]	[.....]
36	0APE ₃₆	13874 ₁₀	$Z..G*(F-(E+D-C))+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1$

Obviously, in case there is no need to ‘increase the base’ the ‘*...’ part can be ignored:

Base	Integer	Integer	Crazy Sequential Representation
17	254F ₁₇	0011354 ₁₀	$1^2+3/4*5*6*7*8*9-A+B+C+(D-(E+F-G))*...$
17	254G ₁₇	0011355 ₁₀	$1*2+3/4*5*6*7*8*9-A+B+C+(D-(E+F-G))*...$
17	2550 ₁₇	0011356 ₁₀	$1+2+3/4*5*6*7*8*9-A+B+C+(D-(E+F-G))*...$

Notes

Authors consider genuine crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

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